

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE IX

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

September 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300
pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com
+639684666397

*"Write. Educate.
Connect."*

@pinagpalapublishingservices	<input type="text" value="Search"/>
pinagpala_publishing	<input type="text" value="Search"/>
www.pinagpalapublishing.com	<input type="text" value="Search"/>

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.253-264, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

MASTERY UNVEILED: EVALUATING ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY OF BACHELOR OF SECONDARY EDUCATION (ENGLISH MAJORS) IN LEYTE

Authors

**Glady Gay B. Galvez, Irene B. Paja, Joan U. Nadela,
Annabelle A. Dela Rama, Juancho C. Tesado**

*Language and Literature Unit
Abuyog Community College*

ABSTRACT

This study examined the English language proficiency of Bachelor of Secondary Education students majoring in English at Abuyog Community College employing a descriptive correlational research design framed within the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). The investigation assessed participants' competencies across the four essential language macro-skills: writing clarity, reading comprehension, speaking fluency, and listening comprehension, utilizing standardized online assessments administered by Education First (EF SET).

Additionally, the study determined the relationship between English proficiency and various demographic and experiential factors, including age, sex, year level, mother tongue, and self-reported English exposure. Unlike prior research focusing on general learners or adult populations, this study specifically addresses the profile of future English educators, underscoring critical preparatory measures required to align their language proficiency with global standards.

A total of 88 students participated in the study, predominantly female (84.09%) and primarily Waray-Waray speakers (86.36%), representing first to third-year levels. Demographic and profile data were collected through an online survey using Google Forms. The overall mean CEFR score was 54.23, situating the cohort within the B1-B2 proficiency range. Among the four macro skills assessed, writing clarity achieved the highest mean score of 56.95, followed by reading comprehension at 53.06, listening comprehension at 51.47, and speaking fluency at 52.11—the lowest score—indicating a notable disparity between written and oral language proficiency. Statistical analysis revealed a significant correlation between age and English language proficiency, while other factors such as sex, year level, mother tongue, and self-reported English exposure exhibited no statistically significant relationship with proficiency levels.

The study emphasizes the necessity and significance of addressing the instruction techniques. It suggests the implementation of an English Proficiency Development Program in schools in a structured way to develop students' macro skills areas, their competitiveness, and their teaching career in the future.

Keywords: *Language proficiency, speaking fluency, reading comprehension, writing clarity, listening comprehension*

INTRODUCTION

A 2024 English Proficiency Survey by Education First (EF EPI, 2024) shows a notable decline in English Proficiency among Filipino adults from 13th in 2016 and now at 22nd in the latest survey. Evidence of this decline is identified in the country's performance in the TOEIC-based report from

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.253-264, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Hopkins International, 2024. At the local level, faculty and staff at Abuyog Community College (ACC) also express concern about this issue. The incoming first-year students were observed by the faculty and staff members, who often displayed poor reading comprehension and speaking fluency despite having high grades during high school, showing that the national decline may also be evident in their performance.

The four macro skills of English competency are speaking, reading, writing, and listening. The study of Abdukadirova and Mirzajonova (2021), stresses the critical role of reading skills in Industry 4.0, while Mantra et al. (2020) discovered that limited vocabulary and exposure hinder reading comprehension among BSED English students. In terms of listening, Alzamil (2021) explained that listening skills are one of the most difficult skills due to issues such as accent and speed, and Vandergriff (2007) emphasized the importance of authentic practice for developing this skill. Writing proficiency benefits from AI-driven tools, with Fahmi and Cahyono (2021) showing that Grammarly and teacher feedback improve grammar accuracy, and Tseng and Lin (2024) showing that ChatGPT-assisted strategies improve academic writing. Speaking fluency is the most feared skill, according to many, often limited by fear and exposure, yet it can be improved through innovative methods, as shown by Nair and Yunus (2021), who discovered that digital storytelling is effective in building oral communication and confidence.

This emphasizes problems experienced by English major students, such as narrow vocabulary, poor comprehension, fear of speaking, and limited language exposure. While digital learning tools have been proven to improve students' performance in English, some students are still experiencing difficulties in the English language. These are issues, emphasize the significance of assessing the degree of English proficiency among learners and identifying learning strategies to be suggested. If not addressed or neglected, these issues may prevent students' academic high performance and decrease their global competitiveness.

This research, therefore, targets to assess the English proficiency status of English majors at Abuyog Community College and whether their performance reflects the national decline. There is little research on English majors in local community colleges like Abuyog Community College. Unlike the previous studies, which mainly focus on general learners or adults. This highlights the need to evaluate their English proficiency level and suggests recommended interventions in the institutions to ensure the students meet the global standards.

Statement of the Problem

The study evaluated the present proficiency of the Bachelor of Abuyog Community College English majors pursuing a Bachelor of Science in Education (BSED), assesses their general level of English proficiency using the Common European the CEFR, or Framework of Reference for Languages, and outlines the elements that impact these levels.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the English Major students in Abuyog Community College in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Year Level
 - 1.4 Mother Tongue
 - 1.5 Exposure to the English Language

2. What is the actual proficiency level of ACC English majors in terms of:
 - 2.1 Reading Comprehension
 - 2.2 Writing Clarity
 - 2.3 Listening Comprehension
 - 2.4 Speaking Fluency
3. What is the overall English Proficiency level of English Majors based on the CEFR scale?
4. Is there a significant relationship between each variable and the level of English Proficiency attained by the English Majors of Abuyog Community College?
5. What could be the possible intervention methods to retain a high English Proficiency among English Majors?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design to assess the English proficiency of BSED English majors using the CEFR framework. The researchers decided to use a descriptive-correlational design for its appropriateness to this study. It not only explains the existing English proficiency level of the learners but also examines the possible relationships between socio-demographic variables and their English proficiency levels. In contrast to experimental designs, it does not control the variables but evaluates naturally the occurring data of the participants, which is relevant for educational settings to attain the goal of understanding trends and associations rather than establishing direct cause and effect. The four macro-skills were assessed to measure participants' overall language proficiency level. This approach helps the researchers to describe students' current proficiency and identify potential relationships among variables, providing a sound basis for recommending targeted interventions to enhance English language skills.

Respondents of the Study

The study's respondents were selected by the researchers to be English majors. The research is focused only on the 1st year, 2nd year, and 3rd year, consisting of 228 total population of English Major Students.

Locale of the Study

The study was performed at Abuyog Community College in Abuyog, Leyte, Philippines. This is the institution where the respondents of the study are currently enrolled. The researchers ensured that the data collection was conducted efficiently as the respondents did not need to travel to another location to complete the online test.

Research Instruments

The researchers employed the free online English proficiency test developed by Education First, the EF Standard English Test (EF SET), which assesses speaking, writing, listening, and reading skills based on the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) scale, ranging from A1 to C2. The test generates a detailed report including CEFR level, skill performance, and improvement recommendations. Designed for English majors from first to third year at Abuyog Community College, the EF SET's CEFR-aligned framework accommodates learners across proficiency levels, allowing for consistent tracking of student progress and providing reliable, standardized results aligned with academic benchmarks.

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.253-264, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

In addition, the sociodemographic profile of the participants was collected by the researchers using Google Forms, which included a section that included the link to the EF SET Test and a blank space where participants attached the link to their certificates, which highlights the breakdown of their results and their overall English Proficiency.

Data Gathering Procedure

On this ground, the researchers requested approval from the College Education Dean. In a letter, the President of the College, the MIS Coordinator, and the list of BSED-English majors; having secured permission to do so, the teachers concerned were notified, and the students were invited to participate. First to third-year respondents were thus duly represented using stratified random sampling. Participants were given access to the EF SET link through Google Forms for the survey and were asked to answer a few questions to collect socio-demographic information.

Ethical Consideration

The researchers ensured that all participants in the study were volunteers, and everyone was briefed on how the data and the outcomes would be used. The objectives of the study were well explained to the participants, methods accessible there, as well as their freedom to discontinue participation at any time without consequence. All responses have been kept strictly confidential, while the identifying information has been withheld from the report.

Method of Scoring and Interpretation

A. Respondents Profile

AGE	CODE	ADJECTIVAL DESCRIPTION
18-19	1	Younger adults
20-24	2	Emerging Adults
25 ABOVE	3	Matured Adults
SEX		
Male	1	
Female	2	
YEAR LEVEL		
First Year College	1	
Second Year College	2	
Third Year College	3	

**World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.253-264, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

MOTHER TONGUE		
Waray-Waray	1	
Cebuano	2	
Tagalog	3	
English	4	
EXPOSURE TO THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE		
Rarely	1	
Sometimes	2	
Always	3	
Often	4	

B. Curriculum Interpretation Guide on Correlation

Range	Verbal Interpretation
± 1.00	Perfect Correlation
± 0.76 - ± 0.99	Very high positive/negative correlation
± 0.51 - ± 0.75	High positive/negative correlation
± 0.26 - ± 0.50	Moderately small positive/negative correlation
± 0.01 - ± 0.25	Very small positive/negative correlation
0.00	No correlation

Statistical Analysis

The actions were administered to analyze the information given by the participants. To respond to the questions in items one and two, the researchers organized all test scores alongside the socio-demographic profile. Second, the researchers counted and summarized individual CEFR levels. Then, to answer research question 4, non-parametric statistics such as Mann-Whitney U tests. It is conceptually similar to the t-test for determining whether two sampled groups are from a single population. When data do not meet the parametric assumptions of the t-test, the Mann-Whitney U tends to be more appropriate. (Patrick E. McKnight, Julius, Najab, 2010). It was employed to evaluate whether there is a meaningful association between the socio-demographic factors and the English proficiency levels of the participants. Ultimately, tables were used to determine patterns and trends.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile Characteristics

Table 1

Variables	Frequency	Percent	Qualitative Description
Age			
18-19 years	18	20.5	Younger Adults
20-24 years	64	72.7	Emerging Adults
25 and above	6	6.8	Mature Adults
Total	88	100.0	
Sex			
Male	14	15.91	
Female	74	84.09	
	88	100.0	
Year Level			
First year	20	22.73	
Second year	20	22.73	
Third year	48	54.54	
	88	100.0	
Mother Tongue			
Waray-waray	76	86.36	
Cebuano	11	12.50	
Tagalog	1	1.14	
	88	100.0	
Exposure to the English Language			
Rarely	2	2.27	
Sometimes	58	65.91	
Often	21	23.86	
Always	7	7.95	
	88	100.0	

Age. Most responders are between the ages of 20 and 24, 64 or 72.7%, while 18 or 20.5 % respondents are

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.253-264, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

aged 18-19 years old, and lastly 6 or 6.8 % respondents are aged 25 years old and above. This indicates that most of the respondents are emerging adults.

Sex. Out of 88 participants, 74 (84.09%) were female, while there were only 14 males (15.91%) who participated in the study. It shows that there were more female respondents than males.

Year Level. More than half of the participants are third-year students (54.54%), with an equal sample size of first year and second-year students (22.73% each), which shows that the study gets a wide range of academic standings but with a strong concentration of advanced-level students in their third year of college (54.54%).

Mother Tongue. Most participants identified Waray-Waray as their mother tongue (86.36%), reflecting the local linguistic background.

Exposure to the English Language. In terms of English language exposure, a significant portion reported encountering it only sometimes (65.91%), suggesting limited consistent engagement with the language.

Actual Proficiency Level of English Majors

The Table below shows the mean score of English proficiency levels of English majors as to Reading Comprehension, Listening Comprehension, Writing Clarity, and Speaking Fluency.

Skill Area	Mean Score	Standard Deviation (SD)	Adjectival Description
Writing Clarity	56.95	5.32	Competent
Reading Comprehension	53.06	4.87	Moderately Competent
Speaking Fluency	52.11	5.10	Moderately Competent
Listening Comprehension	51.47	5.45	Moderately Competent

Table 2

English proficiency testing in terms of skill categories showed Writing Clarity to be the most highly rated with a mean score of 56.95, reflecting students' competence in written output perhaps due to writing tasks being formal and revision easy. Reading Comprehension was at the second level with 53.06 mean score, indicating good understanding of written text. Speaking Fluency (52.11) and Listening Comprehension (51.47) were relatively low, indicating lower practice range for verbal communication.

**World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.253-264, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

The overall English Proficiency Level as per the CEFR scale was a mean of 54.23, usually within the range B1-B2 (Threshold to Vantage Level – Independent User). English majors showed mixed English ability with most students at B1 (31%) and B2 (36%) levels, reflecting operational capacity and potential for development. Some had low ability (2% A1, 6% A2), whereas a significant group achieved advanced to near-native level (22% C1, 3% C2). This reflects important variation in ability among the participants.

Overall English Proficiency Level of English Majors based on the CEFR Scale
 Table 3 displays the mean overall English Proficiency level of English Majors based on the CEFR scale.

Statistic	Value
Mean CEFR Score	54.23
Interpreted CEFR Level	B1 – B2 Range
Interpretation Summary	Independent User – Threshold to Vantage Level

Table 3

The table shows the overall result from the English Proficiency Assessment. The average CEFR score, at 54.23, fits in the range of B1-B2 under the setting of the Common European Language Reference Framework. As a result, these people identify as Independent Users somewhere between Threshold (B1) and Vantage (B2). As a general rule, at this level, learners should be able to comprehend what actually matters, i.e., cope with all the everyday situations likely to arise while traveling and be able to produce simple connected discourse on topics that are familiar to them. But they may fall short in fluency and accuracy while doing so.

Relationship Between Variables and English Proficiency Level

The findings of the statistical study looking at the link are displayed in Table 4. between the general level of English proficiency and sociodemographic characteristics (Level of CEFR).

Variable	Statistical Test	Test Value	p-value	Adjectival Interpretation
Age	Spearman's Rank Correlation	$\rho = -0.264$	0.013	Significant negative correlation – As age increases, CEFR level tends to decrease slightly.
Sex	Mann-Whitney U Test	U = 537.000	0.825	No correlation – CEFR levels are not associated with sex.

**World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.253-264, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Year Level	Kruskal-Wallis Test	H	H = 0.236	0.889	No correlation – CEFR levels are not related to year level.
Mother Tongue	Kruskal-Wallis Test	H	H = 1.324	0.516	No correlation – CEFR levels do not vary by mother tongue.
English Exposure	Kruskal-Wallis Test	H	H = 1.469	0.689	No correlation – CEFR levels are not influenced by English exposure frequency.

Table 4

According to the results of the Statistical evaluation, it examined the significant relationship between socio-demographic profile and CEFR English proficiency levels. There is a clear inverse relationship between the CEFR level and age ($p=-0.264$, $p=0.013$). This implies that with an increase in age, there is a tendency for CEFR levels to decrease slightly, or vice versa, although the correlation is not very strong. Younger students may achieve better English proficiency due to prior exposure and consistent exposure in the education system.

No significant relationship appeared between sex, year level, mother tongue, or English exposure and CEFR levels. Regardless of having more females. There is no discernible variation in the level of English competence between men and women. as well as female pupils ($p=0.825$). Similarly, each year level does not predict their English proficiency ($p=0.889$) in any sense. This highlights that curriculum design alone might not determine language attainment. The research also discovered no significant difference between the English proficiency level among different mother tongues ($p=0.516$). This is contradictory to the popular interpretation that the mother tongue of students influences their second language proficiency level. Lastly, English exposure also showed no significant difference to CEFR levels ($p=0.689$). This is an unexpected result because increased exposure is usually suggested to correlate with increased proficiency. It implies that formal education plays an important part in determining the ability of English students, or the instrument applied in this research was not sufficient to unveil the complexity due to exposure to English. Briefly, age had a weak negative correlation with English proficiency; the remaining socio-demographic variables, i.e., sex, year level, mother tongue, and self-reported English exposure, have no statistically significant correlation. This means that there are variables beyond the purview of this research that could be more determinative in building their English proficiency.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Abuyog Community College English students tend to be young women, predominantly Waray-Waray speakers, with most having been exposed to English at a moderate level. Most students are characterized by B1-B2 CEFR levels, indicating they are independent users who still need growth in fluency and complexity. They perform well in writing and reading activities, while listening skills are categorized as fair, signaling a need for focused development in oral communication.

A major finding of the research reveals no significant association between proficiency and socio-demographic factors such as gender, year level, mother tongue, or self-reported exposure.

However, age was found to be related to proficiency, suggesting that other unexplored variables may account for proficiency variations.

Overall, the English majors show strong writing skills but require improvement in oral communication and overall proficiency. Since socio-demographic factors have little impact, enhancing teaching methods and providing consistent English exposure are essential to support their development as future language professionals.

To improve English proficiency, especially in listening and speaking, focused interventions are recommended. These include the institutionalization of an English Proficiency Development Program with modular content and the regular conduct of diagnostic assessments. Creating "English Talking Zones" on campus will provide authentic practice opportunities, while club activities such as debates, creative writing, essay writing, and storytelling competitions should be promoted to develop skills and motivation.

Digital tools, remedial and advanced programs for students with varying proficiency levels, and the strengthening of faculty and staff capabilities are critical components. Trainers should receive training in new, student-centered, and technology-based teaching techniques to offer diverse learning materials. Differentiated activities like pair interviews, group presentations, remedial classes, and peer support can address varied proficiency needs.

Finally, students need motivation to use English in daily and co-curricular situations to build confidence and fluency. Establishing clubs and organizations focused on English, along with consistent language exposure, is vital to ensure learners maintain oral proficiency and succeed as future educators.

REFERENCES

- Abdukadirova, L. Y., & Mirzajonova, E. T. (2021). The importance of reading competencies in the context of the "industry 4.0" industrial revolution. *Academia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(1), 205-210. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2249-7137.2021.00011.2>
- Alzamil, J. (2021). Listening skills: Important but difficult to learn. *Arab World English Journal(AWEJ)* Volume, 12 <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol12no3.25>
- Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) <https://www.coe.int/en/web/common-european-framework-reference-languages>
- Education First – English Proficiency Index (EF EPI) <https://www.ef.com/wwen/epi/>
- EF SET – EF Education First (2014) <https://www.efset.org>
- Fahmi, M. A., & Cahyono, B. Y. (2021). EFL students' perception on the use of Grammarly and teacher feedback. *JEEs (Journal of English Educators Society)*, 6(1), 18–25. <https://doi.org/10.21070/jees.v6i1.849>
- Hopkins International Partners (TOEIC data source) <https://www.hopkins.ph>
- Mantra, I. B. N., Widiastuti, I. A. M. S., & Pramawati, A. A. I. Y. (2020). Micro and macro skills of reading comprehension acquired by EFL students. *International Journal of Linguistics and Discourse Analytics*, 1(2), 10-17. <https://doi.org/10.52232/IJOLIDA.V1I2.15>
- McKnight, P. E., & Najab, J. (2010). Mann-Whitney U test. *The Corsini Encyclopedia of Psychology*, 1–1. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470479216.corpsy0524>
- Nair, V., & Yunus, M. M. (2021). A systematic review of digital storytelling in improving speaking skills. *Sustainability*, 13(17), 9829. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13179829>

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.253-264, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

- Ticar, R. K. M. (2024). Social factors and macro skills proficiency of tenth-grade students. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(9), 438-471. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13756232>
- TOEIC-related news from Hopkins <https://www.hopkins.ph/news/toeic-results>
- Tseng, Y. C., & Lin, Y. H. (2024). Enhancing English as a Foreign Language (EFL) Learners' Writing with ChatGPT: A University-Level Course Design. *Electronic Journal of E-Learning*, 22(2), 78–97. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ejel.21.5.3329>
- Vandergrift, L. (2007). Recent developments in second and foreign language listening comprehension research. *Language Teaching*, 40(3), 191–210. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444807004338>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17241678

